

Lukasiewicz 25.02.25

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Sample Name: Proszki

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Image

Live Map 1

ElementOverlay

- C K
- O K
- Si K

C K_ROI (105)

O K_ROI (26)

Si K_ROI (52)

kV: 5 Mag: 500 Takeoff: 35 Live Time(s): 1 Amp Time(μs): 50 Resolution:(eV) 138

Sum Spectrum

eZAF Quant Result - Analysis Uncertainty: 10.57 %

Element	Weight %	MDL	Atomic %	Net Int.	Error %
C K	80.3	0.01	89.6	8696.3	7.0
O K	2.6	0.01	2.2	552.1	8.2
Si K	17.1	0.01	8.1	2971.1	5.6